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The impact of textbooks in use for english as a foreign language learner in Beninese educational system

Kottin, Assogba Evariste

Université d'Abomey-Calavi (FLLAC / UAC) - Bénin
Laboratoire du Groupe de Recherche sur l'Afrique et la
Diaspora, GRAD

kottinevariste@yahoo.fr

0009-0002-9679-9269

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Titre	L'Impact des Documents d'Accompagnement Utilisés pour les Apprenants d'Anglais Langue Etrangère dans le Système Educatif du Bénin
Mots clés	Impact ; documents d'accompagnement ; usage ; apprenants d'ALE ; système éducatif ; éducateurs.
Résumé	
<p>L'objectif fondamental de la présente étude est d'examiner l'impact des documents d'accompagnement conçus pour les apprenants d'Anglais langue étrangère dans le système éducatif du Bénin. Les documents d'accompagnement sont conçus et élaborés sous le haut contrôle des ministères des enseignements pour une variété de niveaux et de catégories des apprenants et utilisés dans les environnements de l'enseignement et apprentissage de l'Anglais langue étrangère au cours des années scolaires et académiques. L'exploration des défis pour l'usage des documents d'accompagnement est faite suivant le niveau des apprenants en insistant sur les différentes caractéristiques. Les données sont collectées à travers des questionnaires adressés à 137 apprenants ainsi qu'à travers des interviews conduites avec 13 éducateurs d'Anglais langue étrangère et 15 apprenants d'universités en Anglais. Ces données étaient réunies, transcrites, et analysées, suivant un certain nombre de critères nécessaires dans cette investigation pour la considération d'un document d'accompagnement donné. Les résultats de base exposés à travers plusieurs apprenants, indiquent que les documents d'accompagnement utilisés aux cours d'Anglais langue étrangère étaient à peine accessibles pour le groupe spécifique d'âge d'apprenants au Bénin. Des répondants ont expliqué que plusieurs tâches et des activités mentionnées dans ces documents d'accompagnement n'étaient pas arrangées des étapes les moins difficiles aux plus difficiles en vue d'encourager l'engagement des apprenants. En plus, des activités d'écoute étaient rarement supportées par des enregistrements audios qui devraient avoir été pris en compte dans les documents d'accompagnement. Plus loin, des apprenants espèrent que le livre pourrait contenir des exercices à choix-multiples. Ceci veut dire que certains paramètres de ces documents d'accompagnement sont à réviser, et des enregistrements audios convenables devraient être mentionnés pour supporter les activités d'écoute. Néanmoins, les forces des documents d'accompagnement existent, par exemple, il est à noter que les activités dans les documents d'accompagnement pourraient donner des opportunités qui encouragent l'originalité, la motivation, aussi bien que la curiosité des apprenants.</p>	

Keywords	Impact; textbooks; use; EFL learners; educational system; educators.
Abstract	
<p>The fundamental objective of the current study is to examine the impact of textbooks tied down for English as a foreign language student in Beninese instructive structure. Textbooks are conceived and elaborated through the high control of the ministries of educations for a variety of students' grades and categories and used in EFL teaching and learning settings during school and academic years. The exploration of the challenges for the textbook use is made according to learners' grade emphasizing on different characteristics. Data were collected over and down with questionnaires addressed to 137 learners as well as through interviews conducted with 13 EFL educators and 15 university EFL students. These data were gathered, transcribed, and analyzed, according to a certain number of criteria necessary in this investigation for the consideration a given textbook. The basic findings exposed through the great number of learners, indicated that the textbooks used in EFL classes were hardly accessible for the specific age group of learners in Benin. Respondents explained that several tasks and activities mentioned in these textbooks were not arranged from less difficult to more difficult steps in order to foster learners' involvement. In addition, listening activities were scarcely backed up by audio recordings that ought to have been implied in textbooks. Furthermore, learners hoped the book could contain multiple-choice assignments. This means that certain parameters of these textbooks are to be revised, and the suitable audio recordings should be</p>	

mentioned in order to support the listening activities. Nevertheless, strengths of the textbook occur, for example, it is noticed that activities in the textbook could give opportunities that foster learners' originality, motivation, as well as curiosity.

1. Introduction

The resources used for effective teaching and learning encompass textbooks also designated as coursebooks, which are very fundamental for educators and students because they act as road maps for them. For this reason, Andon (2018) has drawn researchers' attention on the fact that teaching legal forms remain at the acute heart of linguistic morphology instruction. In addition to the constant way for grasping whatever contributes to their innovation that dwells a prominent slice of language educators' skilled improvement. In the opinions of several experts, the English Language Teaching (ELT) textbooks abide the underlying rudiments of EFL instructing and learning. Additionally, they remain prevalently the predominant and inclusively convenient instructing materials used in educational centers. While detailing the fundamental usefulness of textbooks in instructing and learning English as a Foreign Language, Benevento (1984) has argued that any moment foreign language educators gather, the subsequent cardinal utterances and questions: what is the way to proceed? Most of the time, what coursebooks can be made use of?

Moreover, Baker et al. (1989) have observed that coursebooks abide the substantial constituents that outfits majority of students as well as instructors with language lessons. Considering the most prominent intention of the English Language Teaching coursebooks, Byrd & Schuemann, Khoo & Knight (2015) have declared that English Language Teaching coursebooks include two categories of data. These include thematic/issue substance (household, educational centers, etc.) in addition to linguistic elements (grammar, lexical field, as well as abilities).

1.1 Background to the study

Lesson books as well as linked instructing and learning tools and media have been accommodated perpetually to the ever-diversifying and increasing conflicts and requisitions of knowing and mastering EFL. These have also been accommodated catered to innovative discoveries in overseas language investigation and theory building as well as to progressions in knowledge techniques. Consequently, scholarly opinions related to the usefulness of coursebooks in addition to proposals on the way to use it in daily classroom functions frequently reproduces little more than individual viewpoints as well as common sense. Learning is rated as the process of assembling or associating the surroundings to putting up innovative participations.

1.2 Problem statement

A variety of reading texts and activities occurring in coursebooks, question the suitability of the contents of these coursebooks used in EFL classes. Coursebooks remain highest and overwhelming instructing assistance tools for language training in a conventional setting and EFL educators emphasize on these like basic

architectures for their instructions. Students seem indoctrinated by the coursebooks they make use of for learning the language of Shakespeare where they witness social, religious, cultural, and linguistic varieties.

Being intrinsically the same, students hold forth acquaintance with the intellectual achievement intention and far side of the consideration of the document in use introduces a pleasant behavior. This deportment with regard to EFL lifestyle puts forward in the beforementioned documents strenuous for language erudition which implies efficient act of gaining possession and enlightening perception. Comparable to different additional EFL settings, in Beninese educational system, coursebooks abide increasingly accommodated and made to order to reach the societal awareness and the flourishing and varying requests of studying EFL. Consequently, undergraduates come by their paramount interconnection with the target way of life the whole time these unambiguously adjustedly and specialized coursebooks.

1.3 The main objective

The underlying purpose of the ongoing academic work involves inquiring into the influence of coursebooks bound for EFL undergraduates in Beninese educational system. Handbooks are pondered and planned or carried out with great care in the thick of the inflated command of the leaderships of instructions for a diversity of undergraduates' appraisals and classifications and handed-down in EFL instruction and learning surroundings throughout the time of educational institution as well as academic periods. The investigation of the challenges for the benefit of handbooks is made in keeping with undergraduates' and postgraduates' results focusing attention on dissimilar features.

1.4 Research questions

This is one of the most important sections of a research paper; and in the current study, four (4) main interrogations have been carefully assessed and refined as follows:

RQ1: What effect does integral and activity by activity use of textbooks have on EFL teaching and learning inside and outside classrooms?

RQ2: How should EFL teachers make use of textbooks so as to encourage their learners' effective involvement?

RQ3: What are the most effective communicative strategies and techniques suitable for increasing EFL students' interest in textbooks' activities?

RQ4: What are the dissimilarities between EFL teachers who use a textbook in its entirety and those who show their ingenuity and creativity in their classes?

1.5 Research hypotheses

As assertions that skate research questions and give proposals of awaited outcomes, they are also complete portions of the experimentation inquiry that

establish the bases of scrutiny delving practices. For extreme clarity, the four (4) scientific conjectures below articulate about both what undergoes assessments in addition to the presupposed outcomes as:

RH1: Integral and activity by activity use of textbooks can influence negatively EFL teaching and learning inside and outside classrooms because learners' motivation may not be sufficiently raised.

RH2: EFL teachers should make use of textbooks appropriately and create their own activities relevant to their students' cultures and individual needs so as to encourage their learners' effective involvement.

RH3: The most effective communicative strategies and techniques suitable for increasing EFL students' interest in textbooks' activities are: One Quick Question; Assigning New Partners Every Lesson; Dialogue Practice; Creating a Variation of the Dialogue; Communicative Pair Work.

RH4: The dissimilarities between EFL teachers who use a textbook in its entirety and those who show their ingenuity and creativity in their classes are mainly that the former instructors perform less successfully than the latter ones since their classes are quite boring and this lack of learners' motivation impacts negatively their outcomes.

2. Literature Review

Textbooks are prominent from the time when they remain the foundation of entire teaching space instruction which varies from seventy to eighty-five percent (70–95%). Taking into account the improvement of instructive levels as of nursery school over high school, such ascendancy intensifies (Gay, 2000). Internationally, the English Language Learners make use of textbooks as well as supplementary accredited resources as soon as they study English as a subject in educational centers. In line for the countrywide overseas morphological program, unlike English supplies for English Language Learners are technologically advanced for schoolroom practice. These constituents are used to “simplify” the knowledge of English with a diversity of arrangements and occupations to support philological erudition (Tomlinson, 1998: 66). Materials can remain instructional in that they notify students about the linguistic knowledge, and can be empirical because they make available acquaintance to the language tied down, they can be elucidative in that they encourage etymological expenditure, or they can be investigative since they search for detections about etymological routine. (ibid.)

Notwithstanding the instructional, pragmatic, elucidative, in addition to investigative meanings of English textbook resources, there occur discussions and several comments concerning the textbook used for linguistic instruction. Tomlinson (2001) acknowledged the textbook exponents who consider the textbook to be the “greatest suitable arrangement” of provisions demonstration, accomplishing the “uniformity and persistence,” providing initiates a sense of “organization,

interconnection, as well as evolvement,” and assisting educators “get ready” and students “appraise” (p. 67). Tomlinson correspondingly allowed the textbook challengers, for instance, Allwright (1981), O’Neil (1982), Littlejohn (1992), besides Hutchinson and Torres (1994). Rudimentary Interactive Forthcoming Expertise and Reasoning ... who disclosed the disadvantages of textbooks, such as in existence of “unsurprisingly insincere in addition to reductionist” in the attention of etymological opinions as well as in the establishment of verbal familiarity, worsening in meeting the “miscellaneous requirements of its consumers altogether,” imposing the “homogeneity” of prospectus besides methodology, in addition to eradicating the “inventiveness and supremacy” from instructors (Tomlinson, 2001: 67).

Additionally, then the polemics over the textbook expenditure, further differences of opinion carry on about the textbook in addition to appropriate supplies learning or acquisition concentrated, unspontaneous or trustworthy manuscripts, and resources be expurgated (Tomlinson, 2001). Soars and Soars (1996) as well as Hutchinson (1997) perceived that, notwithstanding the consideration on the sensible learning and subliminal achievement continues (Ellis, 1999), the great majority of textbooks are established on the form-focused education with a supplementation of communicational activities. For the duration of the 1990s, investigators, for example, Bacon as well as Finnemann (1990), Kuo (1993), and Little, Devitt, & Singleton (1994) were in favor of the legitimacy of textbook resources in addition to their appealing outcome on initiates, despite the fact that others, such as Day and Bamford (1998), notified the “cult of genuineness” (p. 54). Ellis (1999) contended for the “supplemented contribution” which compromises the feedback with the “paradigms of the objective arrangement in the background of activities concentrated on connotation” (p. 68).

Excepting the legitimacy of comprehensive textbooks, the restriction question is also provocative. Nevertheless, certain procedure of the control of English textbooks might be “academically required” and “parsimoniously essential” (Tomlinson, 2001, p. 68), educators like Wajnryb (1996) criticized the weakness of English as a Foreign Language textbooks. Jacobs and Schumann (1992) and Arnold (1999) contended for the consequence in the confrontational manuscripts that arouse the commitment required for enhanced education. All over the world and locally, an accumulative number of the English language textbooks and resources remain in reproduction and routine. A number of tendencies with the publication of these instruction and knowledge supplies are identified, for instance, a connection in the presentation, practice, and production (PPP) methodology (Tomlinson, 1999), a countless highlighting on the linguistic procedure, and the uniqueness of sentence structure in subordinate and transitional level textbooks (Hutchinson, 1997; Soars & Soars, 1996).

These resources make use of corpus information to reproduce tangible etymological practice (Fox, 1998), calling for student speculation with additional collaborative education correspondences (Parish, 1995) for findings (Bolitho &

Tomlinson, 1995; Carter & McCarthy, 1997; Joseph & Travers, 1996). These significant tendencies in English textbooks for linguistic initiates comprehensively are demonstrated in this study. In the course of the interviews with the respondents on their past and contemporary hypothetical English knowledge understanding, they communicated points of view on the English language textbooks used inside and freestanding the educational centers and their encouragements on the life-threatening temperaments that they have confidence in indispensable the minute they obtaining Institution of higher education English for Academic Purposes. The Place of Handbooks in the EFL Classes: As Zeng & Takatsuka (2009) have explored English as a Foreign Language undergraduates and postgraduates' utterances in simultaneous practice-oriented data processor-interposed connections. The emphasis occurs on whether undergraduates and postgraduates take part each and every one in digital discourses concerning the terminology implementation shadowing the assignment target.

The respect of perspective as well as the way learners' reciprocal commitment influence their etymological knowledge. The pronouncements gave away that novice lent a hand each other in concentrating on morphological configurations from first to last shared information flow. This phenomenon accordingly heightened students' verbal communication ascertaining. Yasemin (2009) talks over an estimation of the English school manuals recommended on behalf of expenditure in position 4 tutorial groups in national primary educational center. According to the research of Sznajder (2009), at the same time as a good number of intellectuals come to an understanding that representations are supposed to be contained within English for Concentrated Single-mindedness programs of study. This inclusion is essential to the same degree a hypothetically perplexing line of work in resounding morphological picking up, is nonetheless not wholeheartedly unblemished which figures of speech are duty-bound to be taught. In the research paper in progress, representational terminologies as well as formulations on or after the abovementioned English handbook remained discriminated alongside the depictions compartmentalized in a prototype of the magazine and academic journal articles' aggregate.

As far as Chen (2008) is concerned, data in addition to communication expertise come up with have emotionally impacted morphological coaching in EFL scholastic systems. It is noticed that instructor's jogging remains convincing for Internet assimilation initiation by the educationalists of English as a foreign language (EFL) in arctic Taiwanese elevated education institutions. Unremitting specialized improvement concentrated on machinery solicitation in morphological education is of the essence. Richards, Tung & Ng (1992) testified that English instructors apprehended a series of comparatively harmonious credence communicating to such deliveries to the same degree the characteristics of the program of study, the responsibility of English in the general public, the applicability of presumption to run through, the trainers' function in the teaching space, and supplementary achievements. Sheldon (1988) has propounded more than a few additional right

minds for textbook appraisal. This author puts forward that the choice of an English Language Teaching course book repeatedly makes signs of a high-ranking managerial and didactic pronouncement in which there is sizeable skilled, pecuniary, or at the same time constitutional capital spending.

An exhaustive evaluation, consequently, would make possible the decision-making and instruction human resources of an unambiguous institution or organization to show favoritism flanked by the whole kit and caboodle of the untaken textbooks for sale (David, 2001). In the study of Ruben (2010), a subject matter scrutiny of the school books used in the Dutch premature upbringing trainer edification illustrates unblemished discrepancies by means of the premeditated prospectus. Neither the substance customary unearthed in the proficient side view for educationalists nor the content requirements on or after the instructive profile of their education practices are satisfactorily shielded in the manuscripts. Despite the fact that they compensate sizeable responsiveness to the instructor's didactic responsibilities, additional undertakings outside the most important exertion course of action are either exchanged in immeasurably a smaller amount of taskforce or passed over completely. Moreover, there occur incorporating the compulsion for premeditated prearranging, for mirror image and estimation, for the advancement of instructive guiding principle, and for teamwork as well as relationship with collaborators from supplementary branches of learning and teaching.

Authors such as Marc and Kees (2009) scrutinize the substance of teaching manuals over and above educators' convention of them. It is noticed that instructors have progressively more implemented textbooks that took into account learners' predilections extremely. These inclinations give the impression to remain the answer of new circumstance in the learners' inhabitants more willingly than instructors' certified descriptions. Some studies signpost that EFL teaching manuals are taken advantage of in countless distinguishing predicaments, being influenced by an off the mark continuum of components. The educator looks as if he/she were the factor of the highest prominence. Among knowledgeable publications, there occur several preliminary manuscripts to instructing English as a foreign language, various first choice or panaches of coursebook expenditure remain acknowledged and labelled in there or thereabouts detachment (Haß, 2006). Furthermore, there occur fluctuating from all-embracing textbook-dependence to additionally careful methodologies, on or after the heterogeneous use of numerous unlike tutoring resources. Theses personalities play very crucial roles to the engagement of celebrity-finished backgrounds, outstandingly in undertaking-focused on or undertaking-established categorizations of teaching.

In the current perspective, coursebook-constrained instruction stays repeatedly established in disapproval to additional accommodating methodologies to coursebook expenditure. The latter is frequently appreciated to the same extent the most satisfactory, substantiating and suitable. English lessons manuals in instructing and initiating lessons documents stay a starting point within educational center

prospectuses all-inclusively, displaying educators as well as learners with the authorized expertise of school disciplines in addition to the favored tenets, methodologies, abilities, and experts' comportments. Schoolbooks are possessions, governmental intentions, and traditional exemplifications and, consequently, are the location and upshots of exertions and cooperation with the intention of regulating in what manner and by which person they will be constructed, in what manner and by which individual their substances will be preferred, in what manner and to which person they will be disseminated, and in what manner educators and learners will make use of them (Shannon, 2010).

The amalgamation of morphological as well as matter education is of strengthening appeal in second and foreign language programs at basic, secondary, and tertiary junctures from place to place in the whole biosphere (Short, 2006). According to Joan (2001), investigations have been exhibited on the capability of transitional-concentrations' English as a Foreign Language grammar schools manuals to give learners control of schooling, established on the authors of lesson manuals arrangement of learners' resolution making contingencies in undertakings. Different tasks in coursebooks remained dissected for the likely regulator of learning conditions communicated to gist selection, technique opportunities, and evaluation procedures. It is stated that learners hypothetically have few choices and thus little control of the educational process. The main stream of assignments possibly will prepare learners for the most part for civil service employments even though the single-mindedness on satisfactory responses ought to hold back etymological erudition.

English as a Foreign Language instructors require to act as a go-between a lesson manuals' impending to have power over if the ambition is to originate the undergraduates and post graduates who come up with a little domination over their identifiable erudition in the course of prospectuses decision making. In keeping with Cortazzi and Jin (1999), textbooks can be an instructor, a diagram, a resource, a mentor, an expert, and principles. Consequently, the lesson manual can be a most important starting place of traditional rudiments above and beyond making available morphological and newsworthy substances which unescapably replicate the philosophy fundamental in the EFL framework of an individual crowd. Feryok (2008), declares that aforementioned research has revealed that instructor perceptions as well as practices could be contradictory, outstandingly in the company of allegations on the order of communicative instruction routines.

3. Methodology of the Study

Writing a methodology stays a cardinal chunk of displaying enquiries' discoveries to the community. The methodology holds up researchers' outcomes by rationalizing their investigation procedures and forming a ground plan of the way they got hold of their deduction. They award the case for the reason of the choice of the methods handled and account for the means by which these procedures in a straight line headed to responses to the interrogations outstretched in their study. In

the current study, the data collection took place all the way through the administration of questionnaires sheets to one hundred and thirty-seven (137) undergraduates and post-graduates in addition to the interviews directed to thirteen (13) EFL instructors as well as fifteen (15) university English as a Foreign Language learners. From these research populations (137: Questionnaire to EFL Learners; 13: Interview with EFL Teachers; 15: Interview with University EFL Learners), the following sample sizes are respectively deduced: (137 = Sample size = 70; 13 = Sample size = 12; 15 = Sample size = 14) These data were mustered, transliterated, and inspected, in proportion to innumerable criteria compulsory in this study for the introspection an assigned lesson manual.

3.1 Questionnaire to EFL Learners

On the questionnaire sheets addressed to EFL students in some secondary schools, these participants have to say mainly whether the integral use of textbooks influences negatively EFL teaching and learning. Next, they should judge whether activity by activity use of textbooks influences negatively EFL teaching and learning. In addition, these learners could judge if the integral use of textbooks influences positively EFL teaching and learning. Then, it was also necessary for them to justify have activity by activity use of textbooks influences positively or not EFL teaching and learning. Moreover, these respondents ought to answer whether EFL teachers should use textbooks integrally for their learners' effective involvement. Finally, they show if EFL teachers should use textbooks scarcely for their learners' effective involvement.

3.2 EFL Teachers' Interview Guide

The interviews conducted with EFL educators enabled them to provide answers to four (4) main questions. Firstly, they are to demonstrate whether EFL teachers should avoid using textbooks for their learners' effective involvement. Secondly, they are asked to explain deeply and clearly how verbal communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students' interest in textbooks' activities. The third question has made them justify the way non-verbal communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students' interest in textbooks' activities. At last, such instructors have to substantiate why visual communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students' interest in textbooks' activities.

3.3 EFL University Learners' Interview Guide

Interviews shepherded in the company of EFL University students empower them to make evident the predicament written communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students' interest in textbooks' activities. Afterwards, these learners should show support whether there are no dissimilarities between entire EFL users of a textbook and ingenious and creative user. Additionally, they are to vindicate if there are several dissimilarities between entire EFL users of a textbook and ingenious and creative user. Conclusively, these respondents are asked to judge

whether there are only dissimilarities between entire EFL users of a textbook and ingenious and creative user.

4. Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1 Questionnaire to EFL Learners’ Results-(70= 100 %)

Tableau 1: Learners’ Viewpoints.

Statements	Positive Answers- Yes-%	Negative Answers- No-%	Total- 70- 100%
integral use of textbooks influences negatively EFL teaching and learning	32- 45.71%	38- 54.28%	70- 100%
activity by activity use of textbooks influences negatively EFL teaching and learning	36- 51.42%	34- 48.57%	70- 100%
integral use of textbooks influences positively EFL teaching and learning	28- 40.00%	42- 60.00%	70- 100%
activity by activity use of textbooks influences positively EFL teaching and learning	22- 31.42%	48- 68.57%	70- 100%
EFL teachers should use textbooks integrally for their learners’ effective involvement	20- 28.57%	50- 71.42%	70- 100%
EFL teachers should use textbooks scarcely for their learners’ effective involvement	10- 14.28%	60- 85.71%	70- 100%

Table 1 shows that thirty-two (32) respondents (**45.71%**) have confessed that integral use of textbooks influences negatively EFL teaching and learning, whereas thirty-eight (38) participants (**54.28%**) have objected. Next, it is noticed that while thirty-six (36) respondents (**51.42%**) have said that activity by activity use of textbooks influences negatively EFL teaching and learning, thirty-four (34) participants (**48.57%**) are against. Moreover, as twenty-eight (28) participants (**40.00%**) have answered that integral use of textbooks influences positively EFL teaching and learning, forty-two (42) of them (**60.00%**) have not accepted. In addition, twenty-two (22) participants (**31.42%**) have said that activity by activity use of textbooks influences positively EFL teaching and learning but forty-eight (48) participants (**68.57%**) have rejected this opinion. It is also noticed that twenty (20) participants (**28.57%**) have thought EFL teachers should use textbooks integrally for their learners’ effective involvement but fifty (50) of them (**71.42%**) are opposed to this idea. Finally, it is noticed that ten (10) respondents (**14.28%**) have believed that EFL teachers should use textbooks scarcely for their learners’ effective involvement whereas sixty (60) of them (85.71%) have strongly rejected.

4.2 Interview with EFL Teachers’ Results-(12= 100 %)

Tableau 2: EFL Teachers’ Opinion.

Statements	Positive Demonstration	Negative Demonstration	Total-12= 100 %
EFL teachers should avoid using textbooks for their learners’ effective involvement	00=00%	12= 100 %	12= 100 %
Verbal communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students’ interest in textbooks’ activities	12= 100 %	00= 00 %	12= 100 %
Non-verbal communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students’ interest in textbooks’ activities	12= 100 %	00= 00 %	12= 100 %
Visual communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students’ interest in textbooks’ activities	12= 100 %	00= 00 %	12= 100 %

Through table 2, none of the respondents have accepted that EFL teachers should avoid using textbooks for their learners’ effective involvement but all of them, twelve (12) participants (100 %) have rejected this idea. 12 participants (100 %) have demonstrated clearly that verbal communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students’ interest in textbooks’ activities and none of them have accepted. 12 respondents (100 %) have explained that non-verbal communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students’ interest in textbooks’ activities, whereas none of them have opposed. Finally, twelve (12), all of the participants (100 %) have argued that visual communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students’ interest in textbooks’ activities but no one has rejected.

Figure 1: EFL Teachers' Integral Use of Textbooks in their Classes (Source: Field Study, 2024).

Figure 1 shows that interviewees’ reactions are positive through the total population’s agreement (12-100%). Consequently, they have all accepted the item 1, the opinion that EFL teachers' integral use of textbooks in their classes can favor only a little learners’ reading proficiency (35%). Next, through Item 2, the twelve interviewees have recognized that very few learners (13.5%) can gain oral communication proficiency with EFL teachers' integral use of textbooks in their classes. In addition, they have all agreed that the degree of problem-solving proficiency (Item 3) with this way of using textbooks is too low (11.5%), whereas only a few learners (40%) are said to gain writing proficiency (Item 4).

4.3 Interview with University EFL Learners’ Results-(14= 100 %)

Tableau 3: University EFL Postgraduates’ Perspectives.

Statements	Positive Demonstratio n	Negative Demont stration	Total- 14=100%
Written communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students’ interest in textbooks’ activities	14=100%	00=00%	14=100%
There are no dissimilarities between entire EFL users of a textbook and ingenious and creative users.	00=00%	14=100 %	14=100%
There are several dissimilarities between entire EFL users of a textbook and ingenious and creative user.	14=100%	00=00%	14=100 %
There are only dissimilarities between entire EFL users of a textbook and ingenious and creative user.	00=00%	14=100 %	14=100%

Figure 2: EFL Teachers' Ingenious and Creative Use of Texbooks in their Classes (Source: Field Study, 2024).

Figure 2 indicates that contenders’ collaborations are tangible in the course of the global population’s agreement (12-100%). Consequently, they have all accepted

through all of the items the opinion that EFL Teachers' Ingenious and Creative Use of Textbooks in their Classes can favor the equilibrium of language skills, language subskills, and language functions. For example, learners' reading proficiency's degree is very high (24.55%). Next, through item 2, the twelve interviewees have recognized that EFL teachers' ingenious and creative use of textbooks in their classes fosters learners' oral communication proficiency (25.38%). In addition, they have all agreed that the degree of problem-solving proficiency (Item 3) with this way of using textbooks is also very high (24.45%). Finally, Learners mainly acquire writing proficiency (item 4-25.62%).

4.4 Interview with University EFL Learners' Results-(14= 100 %)

Tableau 4: University EFL Postgraduates' Perspectives

Statements	Positive Demonstration	Negative Demonstration	Total- 14=100%
Written communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students' interest in textbooks' activities	14=100%	00=00%	14=100%
There are no dissimilarities between entire EFL users of a textbook and ingenious and creative user.	00=00%	14=100%	14=100%
There are several dissimilarities between entire EFL users of a textbook and ingenious and creative user.	14=100%	00=00%	14=100%
There are only dissimilarities between entire EFL users of a textbook and ingenious and creative user.	00=00%	14=100%	14=100%

Table 3 shows that the total number of the participants, fourteen out of fourteen (14=100%) have justified carefully that written communication strategies and techniques increase EFL students' interest in textbooks' activities. None of them have recognized that there are no dissimilarities between entire EFL users of a textbook and ingenious and creative user; they have all accepted (14=100%). 14 participants (100%) have argued that there are several dissimilarities between entire EFL users of a textbook and ingenious and creative user. Finally, none of them have recognized that there are only dissimilarities between entire EFL users of a textbook and ingenious and creative user, consequently, their total number (14=100%) have objected to this opinion.

Figure 3: *EFL Teachers Who Never Use Textbooks in their Classes (Source: Field Study, 2024).*

Figure 3 points out that the participants’ answers are affirmative according to the entire people’s understanding (12-100%). Therefore, they have all acknowledged with all of the elements the position that EFL teachers who never use textbooks in their classes cannot encourage learners’ language skills, language subskills, and language functions. For example, learners’ problem-solving proficiency is almost negative (Item1-00.5%). Then, students’ oral communication proficiency is almost negative (Item2-00.5%). They all recognized that EFL teachers who never use Textbooks in their classes do not favor students’ writing proficiency sufficiently (Item3-03.75%). Moreover, these interviewees have demonstrated that even learners’ reading proficiency’s level is only 06.25% (Item 4). Finally, in Item 5, the gradation of learners’ language proficiency global failure is considerably high (89%).

Figure 4: *Adequate Use of ICT for Innovating Textbooks in EFL Classes (Source: Field Study, 2024).*

Figure 4 displays that respondents’ answers are positive through the total number of the people’s conformity (14-100%). As a result, they have all agreed with all of the items of the statements that the adequate use of ICT for innovating

textbooks in EFL classes can foster the stability of language skills, language subskills, and language functions. Let's say that all participants have argued that undergraduates develop effective and sufficient problem solving and critical thinking proficiency (25.03%) with the adequate use of ICT for innovating textbooks in EFL classes (Item 1). They have demonstrated as well that learners' oral communication proficiency is a reality (Item 2-24.99%). These respondents have also justified deeply that writing proficiency is very high (Item3-25.01%) in addition to reading proficiency that is highly increased (Item 4-24.97%).

5. Discussion

Lesson manuals remain made up and built on within the above average hegemony of the organizations of instructions for a unpredictability of undergraduates and post-graduates' rankings and classifications and depleted in EFL teaching and learning surroundings for the duration of conservatory as well as intellectual years. The consideration of the experiments on behalf of the course manual practice is prepared and arranged in keeping with apprentices' ascent calling attention to far removed from characteristics. Measurements were unruffled from end-to-end feedback forms concentrated to several students in addition to interviews overseen with some EFL trainers as well as a few university EFL postgraduates. The main results have revealed that several partakers have make known that all-encompassing wear and tear of lesson manuals induces deleteriously EFL tutoring and picking up, in spite of the fact that other contestants have taken exception to this statement.

The main findings of the study are in line with the research questions' contents and the research hypotheses. For instance, the first research question inquiries about the effect that unabridged and activity by activity use of lesson written documents have on EFL instruction in addition to erudition inside and outside educational center rooms. Through the first research **hypothesis**, it is conjectured that integral and activity by activity practice of lesson written documents is able to shape offputtingly EFL keeping fit and studying inside and outside teaching space for the reason that beginners' impelling cause may not be necessarily upstretched. Thereafter, it is sighted that at the same time as a considerable number of perpetrators have given away that activity-by-activity usage of textbooks has some unconstructive bearings on EFL instruction and learning, nevertheless, few contenders are in contradiction of such an opinion.

In addition, to the same degree, a handful respondents have countered that integral use of textbooks impels beneficially EFL teaching and learning, most of them have not consented. Furthermore, very few contributors have understood that activity by activity use of textbooks instigates encouragingly EFL teaching and learning. Nevertheless, the majority of these partakers have completely precluded such a stance. Correspondingly, it is perceived that only a few co-conspirators have cogitated EFL schoolteachers should get through textbooks intrinsically in aid of their undergraduates' active commitment contrarily to almost all of these participants

who are in conflict with this conception. To end with this viewpoint, it is deciphered that a very small number of the interviewees have assumed that EFL educators should take advantage of textbooks barely for their learners' vital engrossment conversely, roughly the whole number of them have strappingly thrown out the indication.

The second research question has asked the way EFL educators ought to make use of lesson written documents with the intention of encouraging their educators' unpretentious backing. Consequently, EFL trainers have to make use of textbooks fittingly and generate their identifiable activities right and proper to their learners' humanities and idiosyncratic requirements with the aim of fostering their beginners' successful commitment. Additionally, not a single person among the perpetrators has concurred that EFL educationalists should keep away from getting through course manuals for their students' applicable enthusiasm their total number has discarded the approval. The whole number of results' providers have flaunted unmistakably that outspoken exchange of ideas strategies and techniques strengthen EFL learners' enticement in the variety of activities available in lesson books' and not a soul in their company has entered upon this argument. These performers altogether have put in plain words that non-verbal communication approaches as well as procedures intensify English as a Foreign Language undergraduates' attentiveness in the activities mentioned in textbooks. Not a hint among these interviewees has banned this judgement. Beyond doubt, all of the respondents have debated that pictorial interaction methodologies as well as procedures step up English as a Foreign Language undergraduates' enthrallment in lesson manuals' activities and not a single person has declined.

The third research question is to mention the unbeatable functional communicative policies and procedures seemly for snowballing EFL initiates' approachability in textbooks' activities. Consequently, the high-pitched operative communicative strategies and techniques right and proper for accumulative EFL initiates' helpfulness in textbooks' activities are One Quick Question; Assigning New Partners Every Lesson; Dialogue Practice; Creating a Variation of the Dialogue; Communicative Pair Work. It has been put on view that all these contributors have straightened up cautiously that engraved communication stratagems in addition to processes embolden English as a Foreign Language scholars' mindfulness and enthusiasm in textbooks' activities. They have all acknowledged that there are incongruities concerning absolute EFL manipulators of a textbook as well as imaginative and innovative handlers. These participants have altogether put up with this item. All of them have reasoned that there occur overflowing unconventionalities amid all-embracing English as a Foreign Language users of a course manual and resourceful and productive users. In the end, none of them have been familiar with the opinion that there occur only divergences regarding all-inclusive EFL managers of a course book and pioneering and practical operators. Subsequently, the overall number of them have demurred to this guesstimate.

Finally, the fourth research question requests to be acquainted with the nonconformities that occur between EFL instructive who take pleasure in a course manual in its extensiveness and those who explain their ingenuity and creativity in their classes. Proportionate to this research question, it is believed that there is unsuitableness among EFL trainers who take advantage of a lesson written document in its all-inclusiveness. These include those who are evidence for their exceptionality and resourcefulness in their classes predominantly that the previous instructors act upon less magnificently than the latter ones. This may come true the time when their lessons are moderately mind-numbing and this shortage of tenderfeet's enthusiasm underscores harmfully their aftereffects. Moreover, all of the respondents have deeply demonstrated their positive replies during the course of their total research population's conformity towards the items below. Therefore, they it is argued firstly that the EFL mentors' complete use of lesson manuals in their teaching space can benefit no more than a small number of trainees' reading proficiency. Afterward, it has been identified that hardly any trainees can achieve by word-of-mouth communication proficiency with EFL academics' intact usage of Texbooks for the duration of their teaching sessions. Furthermore, they have wholly established that the gradation of problem-solving proficiency with this manner of take advantage of textbooks is outstandingly near to the ground and only a small number of greenhorns are believed to acquire writing proficiency.

Another category of answers testifies that participations remain substantial in the course of the large-scale population's agreement. Correspondingly, they have all shared the viewpoint that through all of the items the idea that EFL educators' cunning and original usage of lesson manuals in their teaching space is able to encourage the steadiness of language skills, language subskills, and language functions. To the same degree, trainees' reading proficiency's degree is exceedingly in elevation. Thereafter, the claimants have been acquainted with the opinion that EFL educators' ingenious and creative use of textbooks in their teaching space enhance initiates' spoken communication proficiency. As well, they have absolutely come to an understanding that the scale of problem-solving proficiency with this way of taking pleasure in textbooks is also incredibly far above the ground. With no going back, it is believed that undergraduates for the most part assimilate writing proficiency.

It has been highlighted that the respondents' retaliations remain confirmatory in keeping with the all-inclusive commons' settlement. In view of that, all of these interviewees have conceded by means of all the constituents the standpoint that EFL supporters who under no circumstances get through lesson manuals during their educational sessions cannot help newcomers' syntactical skills, linguistic subskills, and etymological undertones. To the same extent, initiates' problem-solving proficiency is almost negative. It follows that, initiates' speaking proficiency is exceedingly unconstructive. They have incontrovertibly been on familiar terms with the viewpoint that EFL mentors who on no occasion get through textbooks during

their training sessions do not bolster learners' lettering proficiency sufficiently. Into the bargain, these contenders have made evident that even the intensity of novices' reading proficiency is exceptionally low. With no going back, the progression of beginners' language proficiency across-the-board breakdown is extensively astronomical.

It has been put on view that interviewees' demonstrations are optimistic from beginning to end the full-blown integer of the individuals' conventionality. Subsequently, they have wholeheartedly reached agreement with all of the elements of the assertions that the suitable procedure of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) for originating course books in EFL teaching and learning sessions. These classes can encourage the immovability of linguistic skills, morphological subskills, and etymological occurrences. This is kept thinking about that all contributors have discussed that initiates build up valuable as well as sufficient problem solving and critical thinking proficiency with the tolerable routine of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) for modernizing lesson manuals in EFL classes. They have equally confirmed that beginners' spoken communication proficiency is a reality. These defendants have additionally rationalized tremendously that writing proficiency is very excessive besides reading proficiency that is approvingly strengthened.

As far as literature review is concerned, very deep-seated and timely relationships can be made. According to Chen (2008), data together with collaboration capability discovered have sensitively overfilled morphological tutoring in EFL collegiate structures. It is spotted that instructors' jogging is convincing for technology learning by the trainers of English as a foreign language (EFL) in freezing Taiwanese raised up training establishments. Unrelenting concentrated enhancement focused on equipment motivation in linguistic coaching is of the lifeblood. Richards, Tung & Ng (1992) have stated under oath that the target language guidance counsellors took in for questioning a succession of abstemiously pleasant-sounding credence. These interlock to such conveyances to the same notch the physical appearance of the curriculum of study, the answerability of English in the unadventurous unrestricted, the applicability of presupposition to impale, the coaches' expediency in the educational center, and corresponding attainments. Sheldon (1988) has promulgated more than a small number of further right minds for lesson written manuals' selflessness. This writer has gone over that the medley of an English Language Teaching lesson written document time after time pressurizes indications of a notable organizational and didactic assertion in which there is extensive qualified, fiscal, or matching decriminalized capital spending.

6. Suggestions

There should be additional and various engagements useful for teaching and learning equipment. They should be consistently updated every 5- or 10-years' time.

The content ought to be more relevant and continually adapted to the circumstances in progress. They have to make allowance for the linguistic as well as cultural assortment of the learners' population without forgetting the noticeable development and renewal of language and technology. The design and configuring in addition to font size of the textbooks should be more as it should be for the initiates' population. Pictures and graphics are supposed to appear more unblemished, additionally fitting for grown-ups and more culturally penetrating. Ability to speak and resonance occurring in audiovisual resources must be more flawless, more trustworthy, and more suitable. This means that the textbooks should be followed by audiovisual materials so as to raise more learners' interest and motivation.

These resources should take into consideration a multiplicity of learning styles. The equipment must be to EFL learners' advantage and ought to be manipulated with a diversity of alignment methodologies. The different teaching and learning tools need to be full of more activities in which students could share preceding cognizance with earlier realization of the content. The appraisal of the importance of commercially obtainable EFL teaching and learning resources is required. Enumerating the whys and wherefores for going through these teaching and learning tools as time density on educators, the unstipulated linguistic proficiency of instructors. The substances' visual request to trainees in addition to the requirement of a paradigm of improvement (Roberts, 1999). Jiang (2006) portrays the morphological customs benefited to put into operation the verbal communication undertaking of suggestions in both native language and EFL textbooks.

Analogies entangling suggestions in two steadfast surroundings in a corpus, university teacher–learner collaboration for the duration of office 60 minutes and learner–learner study groups, and widespread EFL lesson manuals. Along with Los Angeles amalgamated educational locality course book measurement (2002) investigation, the succeeding prototypical requirements, prerequisites instruction methodologies and procedures are handled to valuate course books' usefulness. Four and more language skills should be integrated: speaking, listening, reading, writing. Critical thinking, problem solving. Life skills should also be brought in, in progression rough draft. Receptive skills should be classified before productive. Learners should be made to listen and read before they speak and write. Consequently, suitable activities ought to be scrupulously mentioned in the lesson written manuals, followed by relevant audiovisual materials. Typical learning styles must be integrated as well: aural, oral, visual, kinesthetic. Distinctive approaches and performances should be assimilated and mixed.

Grouping methodologies should be included as well: individual, pair, group and team work. Textbooks must merge advanced level thinking skills and problem solving, which are very useful for language learning and language mastery. Sufficient learners' rehearsal, teaching and learning grammar in context, spiraling activities should be mentioned in the textbooks. Collaborating and communicative procedures, vocabulary, such as objective vocabulary in lesson, reconditioned vocabulary in

lesson. As far as reading is concerned, initiates have to learn how to succeed in pre-reading, reading, post-reading activities and theme reprocessed. Writing activities need to be amalgamated in text without forgetting evaluations and personality estimates at closing stages of modules in addition to ultimate tests.

7. Conclusion

The current investigations have kicked around the pressure of a course book worked up for English as a foreign language trainee in Beninese educational system. Textbooks are weighed up and amplified across the passionate handling of the ministries of teachings for an array of apprentices' ratings and systematizations, and drawn on in EFL lessons and hitting the books circumstances for the period of school and academic years. The examination of the challenges for the utilization of textbooks is completed in accordance with apprentices' grade accentuating out of the ordinary characteristics. Decisions should be bracket together with textbook compilation will have emotional impact on educators, learners, as well as the inclusive teaching space self-motivation. Instructors should be able to answer back to these new trickiness and fluctuations by modifying activities and conceiving the more personalized ones. The preparation of an evaluation enhancement or specification can steer to a further painstaking and exhaustive inspection of prospective textbooks and to superior assumptions for initiates, schoolteachers, and commissioners.

The lesson written manuals are tools, and instructors should have knowledge of not merely by what method to benefit from it, on the other hand exactly how convenient it can remain. The design as well as format are to be rated such as, photographs, type size, color (black, white), layout. There need to occur stride dependable on concentration, upgrading of cosmopolitan consciousness. In this set of circumstances, Burden (2008), through his discoveries has put forward that even though the assessment is determined for formative improvement. Quite a lot of EFL instructors do not slightly get hold of knowledge for the reason that they interrogate mutually the rate of the notifications obtained and the inclusive content validity of estimations as they are cross-curricular and depleted in all courses. Evaluation ought to demonstrate dissimilarity between dissimilarity, contextual, summative assessment and collective methodologies that put on view the productivity and productivity of instruction whereas offering apprentices together with English Language Teaching (ELT) educators' additional ability to speak.

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Biographie de l’auteur

A la fin de ses études secondaires respectivement au CEG Koutongbé (Porto-Novo), CEG Savè et au Lycée Mafory Bangoura (Abomey), Monsieur Evariste Assogba KOTTIN obtint son Baccalauréat série A1 en 1995, et entama ses études supérieures à l’Université Nationale du Bénin (UNB) devenue plus tard Université d’Abomey-Calavi (UAC), où il obtint le DUEL 1 et 2 en 1996 et 1997, la Licence en didactique anglaise en 1999, la Maîtrise en didactique anglaise en 2006, le DEA en linguistique appliquée à la didactique de la langue anglaise en 2013, le doctorat unique en didactique de la langue anglaise en 2016. Il fut inscrit sur la Liste d’Aptitude aux Fonctions de Maître-Assistant en 2020. Il publia plus d’une vingtaine d’articles et participa à plus d’une quarantaine de conférences et colloques à l’international comme à l’interne.